

A New Method To Discriminate Eccentricities In A Three-Phase Squirrel Cage Induction Motor

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This paper describes a new method, the stator instantaneous complex apparent power envelope (SICAPE), for the dynamic simulation of static, dynamic, and mixed rotor eccentricities and for discriminating among them in open- and closed-loop squirrel-cage induction motors. The magnetically coupled circuit model is based on a winding function approach (WFA) to calculate the inductances and their mutuals, allowing all harmonics of magnetomotive force (MMF) present in the stator current spectra to be considered. The FFT method was applied to the stator current at no-load and load conditions, and results were compared to discriminate the characteristic frequency components areas to define eccentricity type. Simulation results show the theoretical accuracy of the technique and the detailed differential equations describing the machine performance effectiveness, and all three mentioned rotor eccentricities that have been discriminated from each other are presented.

Keywords: SCIM, WFA, MMF, SICAPE, FFT.

List of Symbols/Acronyms

f_g — Slip frequency;
 f_{re} — Rotor eccentricity fault component characteristic;
 f_s — Stator frequency;
 L_{sx-y} — Magnetizing Stator inductance per unit length of a coil;
 M_{sr} — Mutual inductance between a stator phase and a rotor mesh;
 M_{rs} — Mutual inductance between a rotor mesh and a stator phase;
 g_0 — Air gap length;
 g — Rotor slip;
 Λ — Air gap permeance;
 r_s — Stator radius;
 r_r — Rotor radius;
 n_{sx} — Stator turns' function;
 n_{rk} — Rotor turns' function;
 δ_d — Dynamic eccentricity;
 δ_s — Static eccentricity;
DTC — Direct Torque Control;
SCIM — Squirrel Cage Induction Motor;
WFA — Winding Function Approach;
MMF — Magnetomotive Force;
SICAPE — Stator Instantaneous Complex Apparent Power Envelope;
FFT — Fast Fourier Transform;
FO — Fractional order controller;
Nb — Rotor bar number;

1. Introduction

During their operation, electric motors can be exposed to different hostile environments or have manufacturing defects [1]. The various internal faults of the motor (such as the short-circuit of the motor wires, the inter-turns short-circuit, broken bearings, the eccentricity of the

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rotor, and broken rotor bars), and the various external faults of the motor (such as phase failure, mechanical overload, locked rotor, and electrical overload) may occur sooner or later [2]. In addition, the wide variety of environments and conditions to which motors are exposed accelerates their aging and subjects them to premature and evolving defects. These types of faults usually relate to the machine's progressive deterioration, which can lead to its stopping if they are not detected promptly.

Significant effort was made in modeling asynchronous machines in the presence of faults such as the break of one or more consecutive bars and/or a portion of a short circuit ring, the inter-turns short-circuit in the windings, and the different types of eccentricities [3].

However, the scientific community is continuing to refine the models dedicated to diagnosis by introducing the effect of slots, saturation, and the non-uniform variation of the air gap, to obtain the most representative model of the induction motor operating with or without a fault [4].

Indeed, many studies have been conducted to develop various methods capable of detecting serious failures and limiting them by avoiding catastrophic failure conditions. Short circuits between stator turns, eccentricity, rotor bar breaks, and bearing faults are the most common faults that can occur in this machine [1, 5, 6].

It is well known that the most widespread method for rotor fault detection, including open-loop machine drive, is motor current signature analysis (MCSA), which relies on signal processing tools such as fast Fourier transforms (FFT) [7, 8].

It depends on detecting sidebands that occur in the stator current spectrum and cause geometric and magnetic imbalances caused by rotor faults. Therefore, these sideband frequencies that appear around the fundamental frequency can be determined, and their amplitudes evaluated and used as a reliable approach to diagnose rotor failure cases.

Moreover, many modern so-called intelligent numerical methods can interfere with diagnosing and detecting faults in the asynchronous machine. However, these methods require expensive technology.

In most cases, diagnostic methods are used for open-loop machine operation. However, in closed-loop drives, control regulators, especially those robust and insensitive to parametric variations, mask and compensate for the fault effect. Therefore, they pose a problem for fault detection when analyzing the stator current. Some attempts can be found in the literature that use other physical quantities for fault analysis, such as active, reactive, and apparent power.

The main goals of this work are the diagnosis and detection of eccentricity faults and the assessment of the severity of the failure when the machine is operating in a closed-loop drive application at variable speed. The DTC strategy equipped with a speed regulator is presented to preserve a high-performance control (Fig. 1). A method used for eccentricity fault detection is based on (SICAPE). This technique was chosen to ensure a good diagnosis despite the control impact.

Fig. 1. DTC control is provided by a PI-OF regulator (Speed Loop)

2. IM model dedicated to eccentricity faults

In an ideal machine, the rotor center is aligned with that of the stator, where they have the same axis of rotation. An eccentricity fault in a perfect IM can manifest at the air gap by the rotor decentering with respect to the symmetry axis [4, 9, 10]. There are three types of eccentricity faults, as shown in Figs. 2.

Fig. 2. Eccentricity Types: a) Static eccentricity; b) Dynamic eccentricity; c) Mixed eccentricity

The IM model is the same as the model mentioned in [11] which is based on the winding function approach, but, the internal IM parameters such as the inductances, constituting a part of the various matrices, must be recalculated analytically to translate best the real physical phenomena encountered by the IM in the healthy or eccentricity fault case [12–14].

Inductance calculations are done using the following expression:

Magnetizing inductance per unit length of a coil $s_{x \leftarrow y}$,

$$L_{s_{x \leftarrow y}}(\theta) = rl \int_0^{2\pi} \Lambda(\theta, \theta_r) n_{s_x}(\theta) N_{s_y}(\theta) d\theta \quad (1)$$

x and y indices represent, respectively the notches occupied by the outward and return movements considered in the coil. Equ. (1) involves three functions:

Air gap permeance $\Lambda(\theta, \theta_r)$: which is represented as the inverse of the air gap length $g(\theta)$ multiplied by the permeability μ_0 .

Fig. 3. Representative diagram of rotor eccentricity.

In IM, the air gap is usually relatively small compared to the rotor radius. Therefore, the rotor rotation axis offset from the stator symmetry axis described by α and β is also small compared to r_r (Fig. 3). The formula for determining the average air gap length without eccentricity:

$$g_0 = r_s - r_r \quad (2)$$

If the rotor center is offset (eccentricity) in Cartesian coordinates (α, β) :

- The stator interior surface $r_s(\theta)$ of radius r_{s0} is considered always stable, and is given by the following equation in polar coordinates (r_s, θ) :

$$r_s(\theta) = r_s \quad (3)$$

- The rotor exterior surface is given in Cartesian coordinates (x, y) by the circle equation:

$$(x - \alpha)^2 + (y - \beta)^2 = r_r^2 \quad (4)$$

The equation (4) transformation to polar coordinates (r_r, θ) is given:

$$\begin{cases} x = r_r \cos \theta \\ y = r_r \sin \theta \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Therefore, the radius $r_r(\theta)$ is determined by a quadratic equation of the rotor exterior surface:

$$r_r(\theta) = \alpha \cos \theta + \beta \sin \theta + \sqrt{r_r^2 - (\alpha \sin \theta + \beta \cos \theta)^2} \quad (6)$$

The air gap length expression is:

$$g(\theta) = r_s - r_r - \alpha \cos \theta - \beta \sin \theta = g_0 - \alpha \cos \theta - \beta \sin \theta \quad (7)$$

Where $g_0 = r_s - r_r$ the average air gap length without eccentricity.

α and β parameters for the air gap length expression, take different expressions depending on the type of eccentricity. δ_s and δ_d represent respectively the degree of static and dynamic eccentricity for the average air gap length g_0 . Note that $\delta_s + \delta_d < 1$ in order to avoid rotor-stator friction.

- **Static eccentricity:** α and β parameters do not depend on the rotor angle θ_r . If assuming the air gap length is uniform, we can assume $\beta = 0$.

$$\begin{cases} \alpha = g_0 \delta_s \\ \beta = 0 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

- **Dynamic eccentricity:** α and β parameters depend on the rotor angle θ_r , no constant term is present.

$$\begin{cases} \alpha = g_0 \delta_d \cos \theta_r \\ \beta = g_0 \delta_d \sin \theta_r \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

- **Mixed eccentricity:** α and β parameters depend on the rotor angle θ_r , and a constant term is present if the air gap length is assumed to be uniform, the constant term in β can be assumed to be zero.

$$\begin{cases} \alpha = g_0 (\delta_s + \delta_d \cos \theta_r) \\ \beta = g_0 \delta_d \sin \theta_r \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

The most approximate expression for the air gap length in case of mixed eccentricity is:

$$g(\theta) = r_s - g_0(\delta_s \cos \theta - \delta_d \cos(\theta - \theta_r)) - r_r \sqrt{1 - \frac{g_0^2}{r_r^2} (\delta_s \sin \theta - \delta_d \sin(\theta - \theta_r))^2} \quad (11)$$

$$\text{Where: } \begin{cases} g(\theta) \approx g_0(1 - \delta_s \cos \theta - \delta_d \cos(\theta - \theta_r)) \\ g_0 \ll r_r \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Note that static and dynamic eccentricity are special cases with $\delta_s = 0$ or $\delta_d = 0$ respectively. The air gap permeance is expressed in the form of a Fourier series, taking into account the rotor eccentricity. Considering firstly only the static eccentricity ($\delta_d = 0$), the permeance function written according to (12) is:

$$\Lambda_{exc,st}(\theta) = \frac{\mu_0}{g_0(1 - \delta_s \cos \theta)} = \frac{1}{2} \Lambda_0 + \sum_{i_{exc,st}=1}^{\infty} \Lambda_{i_{exc,st}} \cos(i_{exc,st} \theta) \quad (13)$$

When only dynamic eccentricity is present ($\delta_s = 0$), the permeance function written according to (12) is:

$$\Lambda_{exc,dy}(\theta) = \frac{\mu_0}{g_0(1 - \delta_d \cos(\theta - \theta_r))} = \frac{1}{2} \Lambda_0 + \sum_{i_{exc,dy}=1}^{\infty} \Lambda_{i_{exc,dy}} \cos(i_{exc,dy} \theta - i_{exc,dy} \theta_r) \quad (14)$$

In the case of mixed eccentricity, the expression of permeance with a combination of both static and dynamic eccentricity:

$$\Lambda(\theta) = \frac{\mu_0}{g(\theta)} = \sum_{i_{exc,st}=0}^{\infty} \sum_{i_{exc,dy}=0}^{\infty} \Lambda_{i_{exc,st}, i_{exc,dy}} \cos((i_{exc,st} + i_{exc,dy}) \theta - i_{exc,dy} \theta_r) \quad (15)$$

Generally, the mixed eccentricity equation (73) is suitable in both static and dynamic eccentricity cases.

- If $\delta_d = 0$, then, (15) = (13), and If $\delta_s = 0$, then, (15) = (14).

2.1 Stator turns' function $n_{s_x}(\theta)$: which represent the conductors' distribution along the stator bore between the forward and return sections of the coil considered.

$$n_{s_x}(\theta) = \frac{N_s}{2} + \frac{2N_s}{\pi} \sum_{v=0}^{\infty} K_{db} \cos \left((2v+1) \left(p(\theta_s - \theta_0) - \left(\frac{2x}{q} - \frac{((2+fracc)q+3)N_e+1}{2qN_e} \right) \pi \right) \right) \quad (16)$$

2.2 Rotor turns' function $n_{r_k}(\theta)$:

$$n_{r_k}(\theta) = \frac{1}{N_r} + \frac{2}{N_r} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} K_{mail} \cos\left(n\left(\theta_s - \theta_r + \frac{1}{2}(2k-1)O_{mail}\right)\right) \quad (17)$$

2.3 Mutual inductance expression between stator phases and rotor meshes

Using the stator winding distribution functions (16) and rotor mesh (17) take the winding coefficients and meshes into account. We examine the following relation, which expresses any mutual inductance between a stator phase and a rotor mesh:

$$M_{sr}(\theta) = rl \int_0^{2\pi} \Lambda(\theta) n_{s_x}(\theta) n_{r_k}(\theta) d\theta \quad (18)$$

Fig 4. Mutual inductances stator/rotor. Taking into account the Fourier series' first 9 harmonics.

- a) Healthy case $\delta_{s,d} = 0\%$, b) Static eccentricity case $\delta_s = 20\%$ and 40% , c) Dynamic eccentricity case $\delta_d = 20\%$ and 40% , d) Mixed eccentricity case $\delta_{s,d} = 20\%$ and 40% .

Mutual inductance expression between a stator phase and a rotor mesh, as already mentioned, is the transposition of $M_{sr}(\theta)$, that is, $M_{rs}(\theta) = M_{sr}(\theta)'$.

Figs. 4 represent the mutual inductances between phases a, b, and c and the first rotor mesh, taking into account the first 9 harmonics of the Fourier series, for healthy case (Fig. 4 (a)), in case of static eccentricity (Fig. 4 (b)), dynamic (Fig. 4 (c)), and mixed (Fig. 4 (d)).

3. DTC and Fractional order (FO) controller description for IM drive

The Direct Torque Control (DTC), and Fractional Order PI (FO-PI) controller for industrial applications of variable speed IM drives are well-detailed (Fig.1) [11] [15, 16].

3.1 Closed-loop IM eccentricity faults detection

The most well-known indices for IM eccentricity faults are the amplitudes of high and low-frequency harmonics appearing on the stator current spectrum. The accuracy frequencies of these harmonics are, respectively as follows [17]:

$$f_{re} = \left(\left(1 \pm k \frac{1-g}{p} \right) f_s \right)_{k=1,2,3,\dots} \quad (19)$$

Where f_{re} is the rotor eccentricity fault component characteristic.

Indeed, the actual location of these components is a function of the number of pole pairs and slips. The interaction of these harmonics with the mainly sinusoidal supply voltage causes eccentricity-specific harmonics in the power and torque spectrum, which appear at the following disturbance frequencies [18–21]:

$$f_{re} = \left(\left(\frac{1-g}{p} \right) k f_s \right)_{k=1,2,3,\dots} \quad (20)$$

4. Simulation results using the (SICAPE) method in open and closed loop IM

In this section, eccentricity fault tests in a cage asynchronous machine are introduced, and the instantaneous apparent power envelope is considered as a good indicator for eccentricity fault diagnosis. In the healthy case, the envelope spectrum shown in Fig. 5 (a) in an open loop contains only the DC component and the frequency component at a frequency equal to $(k f_s)_{k=12}$ in the no-load case, and the component manifests itself at a frequency equal to $(k(1-g)f_s)_{k=12}$ in the loaded case,.

Fig 5. SICAPE apparent power spectrum for healthy IM.
a) In open loop, b) In closed loop.

Otherwise, in a closed loop, Fig. 5 (b) shows only the continuous component, the time-frequency lines caused by the switching of the electronic components constituting the inverter. These time components appeared in the frequency lines in multiples of three $(k f_s)_{k=3,6,9,\dots}$ which causes the appearance of the PSH2, which coincides with $k=15$ for the no-load condition,

but under load, the time components appeared in the frequency lines multiple of six $(kf_s)_{k=6,12,18,\dots}$ and the PSHs disappeared.

Indeed, in the presence of an eccentricity fault, additional components presented in the instantaneous apparent power spectrum (envelope), called the fault's characteristic components, provide additional information for the IM state diagnosis. Therefore, these harmonics can be used as a diagnostic index of static, dynamic, or mixed eccentricity fault when the IM is powered directly by the network (in an open loop) or by a closed-loop control strategy.

4.1 Static eccentricity fault

Apparent power signature analysis is processed for static eccentricity fault detection at degrees of 20%, 30%, and 40% (Figs. 6). The application of FFT is proposed to extract the characteristic frequency components related to the fault. A method of extracting and filtering the apparent power envelope to minimize the switching frequency.

A static eccentricity fault has occurred, causing characteristic frequencies to appear at $f_s + 2f_{re}$, from which it can be noted that the rotor static eccentricity generates frequencies at twice the supply frequency in the case of no-load operation and at more or less the slip frequency f_g in the case of operation under load [19].

Figs. 6 (a) and (b) in an open loop show frequency components equal to $(2kf_{re})$ or $(kf_s)_{k=2,4,\dots}$. Therefore, Figs. 6 (c) and (d) in a closed loop show only the characteristic frequency at fault $(f_s + 2kf_r)$, and the frequency components multiple of three in the no-load case, and those multiple of six in the loaded case.

Increasing the degree of static eccentricity from 20% to 30% and 40% increases the characteristic component amplitude at the fault. This component is unreadable for a low static eccentricity (at a 20% degree) in the closed loop case at no load Fig. 6 (c).

Similar to the MCSA technique, which revealed the characteristic component of static eccentricity defect at $\left(1 + k \frac{1-g}{p}\right) f_s = 3f_s$ for an event ($k = \{4\}$) according to equ. (19), this technique revealed the fault characteristic component at $\left(\frac{1-g}{p}\right) kf_s = 2f_s$ for an event ($k = \{4\}$) according to equ. (20) (Figs. 6). It is observed from the results obtained that the apparent power envelope method has proven to be effective for the static eccentricity faults detection in a closed loop, with an eccentricity degree beyond 20%, according to Figs. 6 (c) and (d), compared to other so-called classical methods.

Fig. 6. SICAPE apparent power spectrum for static eccentricity fault at degrees 20%, 30%, 40%.
 a) Open loop at no load, b) Open loop at 50% load, c) Closed loop at no load, d) Closed loop at 50% load.

4.2 Dynamic eccentricity fault

Figs. 7 presents the theoretical apparent-power signature analysis of the faulty IM for different degrees of dynamic eccentricity, including 20%, 30%, and 40%. It is noted that the frequency components associated with the dynamic eccentricity fault are relatively small compared to those associated with the static eccentricity fault.

In an open loop, Figs. 7 (a) and (b) show the fault characteristic components at frequencies multiple of three, equal to $(kf_s)_{k=3,6,9,\dots}$ at no load, and even at load $(k(1-g)f_s)_{k=3,6,9,\dots}$.

In a closed loop, Fig. 7 (c) shows the fault characteristic component at a frequency equal to $(3f_s)$ which coincides with one of the frequency components multiple of three. While Fig. 7(d) shows the frequency components multiple of three, except that only one component, which represents the fault characteristic frequency, manifests at the frequency multiple of three $(k(1-g)f_s)_{k=3}$. This component has an insignificant amplitude for a dynamic eccentricity degree at 20% compared to the no-load case.

Fig.7. SICAPE apparent power spectrum for dynamic eccentricity fault at degrees 20%, 30%,40%.
a) Open loop at no load, b) Open loop at 50% load, c) Closed loop at no load, d) Closed loop at 50% load,

4.3 Mixed eccentricity fault

The combination of static and dynamic eccentricity faults results in a mixed eccentricity fault. Indeed, the effect of mixed eccentricity fault is more significant on the apparent power spectrum in the frequency domain (Figs. 8) compared to the purely static or purely dynamic eccentricity fault. In addition, characteristic frequency components appear on the lines $(kf_r)_{k=1,2,3,\dots}$, and the mixed eccentricity defect results in the appearance of additional frequencies compared to the cases of static and dynamic type faults.

In an open loop, plus the components that manifest at frequencies equal to $(kf_r)_{k=1,2,3,\dots}$, Figs. 8 (a) and (b).

In a closed loop, Figs. 8 (c) and (d), show the frequency components at $(k(1 - g)f_{re})_{k=1,2,3,\dots}$.

Fig. 8. SICAPE apparent power spectrum for mixed eccentricity fault at degrees 20%, 30%, 40%.
 a) Open loop at no load, b) Open loop at 50% load, c) Closed loop at no load,
 d) Closed loop at 50% load.

5. Conclusion

Firstly, we are interested in analytical modeling of the IM's winding function, dedicated to the eccentricity faults diagnosis, expressed in the three-phase fixed frame linked to the stator and taking into account its different aspects, ranging from the control to the generation of fault indicator signals. The major interest of this model is the fact that it allows the physiological and topological characteristics to simulate its behavior in healthy conditions and the presence of eccentricity fault cases under a DTC control strategy, with a relatively short calculation time. The analytical model was developed and implemented in the MATLAB/Simulink environment. The simulation results show that a static, dynamic, or mixed eccentricity condition can be effectively detected by this approach, whose operating philosophy is based on the spectral component behavior at a frequency of $f_{re} = f_s(1 - g)/p$. Even for low eccentricity levels, or when the machine is operating at no load, the characteristic frequency components are clearly visible. Through the study of different spectral analysis methods in the literature, it can be concluded that the DC component in the spectrum of the complex apparent power module turns out to be a good indicator of the state of the asynchronous machine, despite the high frequency caused by the PWM supply.

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